

Politics in Fisheries Management: Consultation with Fishing Communities in the Indian Ocean, Tanzania

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Abstract:

Fisheries resources are declining globally. The fishers around the globe have been largely blamed for the decline. The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of politics on fisheries management in Tanzania. To achieve this, a qualitative study was conducted in three fishing communities along the Indian Ocean. A total of forty six interviews was conducted. Additionally, six focus group discussions were conducted. Data were analyzed using a content analysis approach. Findings indicate that, politicians influenced sustainable fisheries management efforts in the study areas. This study concludes that, fishers should not be blamed for failures of

sustainable fisheries management initiatives; instead, researchers and fisheries managers need to acknowledge and address several forces that shape and influence fishing practices including politics.

Keywords: *fisheries management, politics, fishing communities, Tanzania.*

Introduction

Sustainable fisheries management is challenging (Jentoft and Chuenpagdee 2009, FAO, 2020). Fisheries management poses challenges which are "complex and tricky" (Jentoft and Chuenpagdee 2009, p. 553). The problems are complex as their causes are diverse. The issues are tricky as they are not as straightforward as one may think.

Fisheries resources remain critical to support people's livelihoods around the globe for its health and wealth. Despite their importance to human beings, fisheries resources are declining globally (FAO, 2014). The decline in fish resources has been well noted by researchers (Allison and Ellis, 2001; O'Reilly *et al.*, 2003; Kimirei, Mgaya, & Chande, 2008; Anticamara *et al.*, 2011; FAO, 2020). This decline has been largely attributed to fishing practices (for example, Pauly *et al.*, 2002; Stobutzki *et al.*, 2006,

FAO 2020). Fishing communities are perceived as reluctant to conform to fisheries regulations (Van der Knaap, 2014; Petit and Shipton, 2012). For example, a study by Obiero *et al* (2015) in Lake Victoria indicates high violation rates of fisheries regulation and that Beach Management Units (BMUs) have limited impact on fisher decisions to comply with regulations.

Nevertheless, research has recognised the role of politics in resource use and management (including fisheries). Ecologists, for example, have noted the role of politics in resource use and management (see Homer-Dixon 1994, Dickens 2004; Benjaminsen *et al.* 2009, Kweyu *et al.* 2020). Benjaminsen *et al.* (2009) assert that local politics play an important role in resource use as some political leaders influence resource use and management plans to meet political goals. In their study of deforestation in Kenya, Kweyu *et al.* (2020) noted that the main

underlying drivers of forest change in the Kenyan context include politics.

In fisheries management, the influence of politics has been recognised as well (see Lubchenco and Grorud-Colvert, 2015; Bush and Marschke, 2016; Aanesen and Armstrong, 2016; Johnsen, 2017; Sonvisen et al., 2017). In their study of small-scale fisheries in South Asia, Bush and Marschke (2016) noted that politics affect environmental problems and potential solutions.

In particular, human beings and fishing communities have been chiefly blamed for the decline in fish catches worldwide. The blame is largely on illegal and unsustainable fishing practices (Petit and Shipton 2012, Van der Knaap, 2014). In the context of Tanzania, our literature review indicates that little attention has been paid to the role of politics and politicians in influencing fisheries management initiatives and the part of politics in non-conformity to fisheries policies and regulations. This study aim to fill the noted gap. The study explores how politics shape or influence fishing practices and contribute to unstainable fishing practices.

Fisheries Management in Tanzania

The Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries Development is Tanzania's highest level of fisheries authority. The Fisheries Division is at the Ministry, which is charged with fisheries in the country to manage, conserve and develop all fisheries resources (URT, 1997). The Division works with Regional Fisheries Offices in regions where fisheries are present. The regional offices are responsible for supervising fishing at the District level. At the District level, there is a District Fisheries Office. This office is responsible for coordination and extension services, law enforcement and surveillance and issuing licenses to artisanal and small-scale fisheries operations as defined in the law. This office collaborates with Fisheries Staff at the Ward and co-management Units (BMU) at the Village levels. The villages form the local government's lowest level in Tanzania and fisheries management. The co-management units at the village level operate in designated landing sites. These co-management units are community institutions known as Beach

Management Units (BMUs). A BMU refers to a group of devoted local stakeholders in a fishing community whose main function is management, monitoring, and surveillance to support the conservation and protection of fish in their locality in collaboration with the government (URT 2003:52). Each BMU formulates its own set of by-laws to meet the specific needs of that particular locality. However, such by-laws should not violate the "mother law" developed and instituted by the Fisheries Division of the Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries Development (the National Fisheries Regulations)

In Tanzania, fisheries management is defined by policy documents that include a set of laws and Acts. The most important ones are the Fisheries Sector Policy Act of 2015 (URT, 2015) and the Fisheries Act No.22 of 2003 (URT, 2003), which provide guidelines for managing fisheries. The BMUs are responsible for enforcing these guidelines at the local level. The primary management strategies include the involvement of key stakeholders in the protection of fish resources, surveillance and the enforcement of the laws by facilitating the formation of BMUs (URT 2003:52). This fisheries management structure is intended to influence and control how fishers interact with fish resources. For example, BMUs were assumed to play a critical role in ensuring the improvement of fisheries management following declines in fish catches in Tanzania (URT, 1997).

Methodology

Study Communities

The study was conducted along the Tanzanian coast on the Indian Ocean at three fishing communities: Kipumbi, Kilwa and Dunda. Kipumbwi is located in Pangani district, Tanga region, Kilwa is in the Lindi region, and Dunda is situated in the Bagamoyo district in the Coast region. These sites were selected because they are among the oldest fishing communities in Tanzania on the Indian Ocean. The study explored how politics influence fishing practices and fisheries management. Thus, the older

fishing communities are assumed to be the most salient locations to provide a better understanding of fisheries over time (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map Showing the Study Communities

Data Collection

This study adopted a qualitative research approach to obtain data on fishing practices and local knowledge of coastal areas in Tanzania.

Data were generated over six months between January and June 2021. In the process, the researcher relied heavily on participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions for all data collection.

Table 1. Number of Interviews, Distribution Among Landing Sites and Demographics of Respondents

Method	Category of Participants	Landing sites					
		Kipumbwi		Kilwa		Bagamoyo	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
In-depth interviews	Fishers/Boat owners	6	1	7	0	8	0
	Fish processors	1	3	1	3	1	3
	BMU leaders	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Fisheries officers	1	0	1	0	1	0
	Elders/ community leaders	1	1	1	0	1	0

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)	FGD-Fishers & boat owners	5	0	8	0	7	0
	FGD – Fish processors & traders	0	6	0	6	0	7

Source: Field Data, 2021

A total of forty-six interviews were conducted in the three study communities over six months, at least 15 interviews were conducted in each study site. Data collection was done in two phases. This enabled the researcher to conduct preliminary data analysis (after the first round) identify gaps, and collect more data during the second phase. Discussions focused on fishers/boat owners, fish processors, fisheries officers, Beach Management Unit (BMU) leaders, and community leaders. A Beach Management Unit consists of a group of devoted local stakeholders in a fishing community whose main function encompasses managing, conserving, and protecting fish in their locality through collaboration with the government (URT, 1997). In addition to key informant interviews, six Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted, two for each village. The first group was with fishers/boat owners, and the second group was with fish processors and traders. FGDs were conducted during the first and second phases of fieldwork. Participants for each focus group were selected from individuals who participated in the key informant interview sessions. Individuals recruited to participate in the focus groups demonstrated a more in-depth understanding of the lake fishery. The FGDs aimed to explore the shared experiences of fishing community members and their perceptions and knowledge regarding ocean fishery as more of a collective, more clearly illustrating shared norms and cultural expectations. Cultural perspective guided this study to explore fishers' knowledge and perceptions regarding the area's fisheries.

Observation was applied throughout the entire process of data collection. The researcher observed major livelihood activities, daily routines of community members, how people interacted with the Ocean, fishing gear used, fish landing, fish processing activities, and fish selling. The observation method was used as

commentary and as a means to confirm what was said by respondents.

Data Analysis

Several stages were involved in data processing. The N-Vivo version 11 software helped sort and organise raw data collected in the fieldwork; this included coding and identifying themes and sub-themes. Then, data were analysed using a thematic approach. During the analysis, one main theme that is related to this study's objective is the influence of politics on fisheries management.

Ethical Considerations

Before data collection began, all procedures for gaining permission to conduct the study involving human subjects were followed. This included receiving final research clearances from all relevant authorities through the Mwalimu Nyerere Memorial Academy. In the field, researchers ensured informed consent by providing clear explanations of the objective of this study to the informants and ensuring that each participant understood that their participation was voluntary and that the information they shared would remain confidential and only be used for this study. Pseudonyms were used in the study to ensure confidentiality.

Results

Politics in Fisheries Management

In the study areas, politics has been an important factor that negatively affects fisheries management efforts. Respondents were asked to explain how politics influenced fisheries practices and fisheries management. Respondents told the researcher that political leaders at local levels (such as villages, wards and districts) are critical people in influencing economic and social development, including

resource conservation initiatives at their locality. However, it was revealed that in some circumstances, this role may conflict with their political goals, resulting in a conflict of interest. In such a situation, a politician may work against the fisheries management efforts to meet their political goals. In an interview with fisheries officers, they mentioned that some politicians work against the same instead of improving fisheries management. In an interview, one fisheries officer noted:-

"Our work as fisheries officers is very challenging. This is because, as we execute our daily responsibilities, we constantly come into friction with politicians. Whenever management efforts collide with the interest of politicians, they normally work against us to meet their political goals" (IDI/fisheries officer/ 2021).

An example was given of what happened at one landing site when fisheries officers were very strict about fisheries regulations. Such officers regularly inspected fishing gear, seized illegal fishing gear and conducted regular patrols in the Ocean. Later on, some politicians intervened to reverse their efforts. One fisheries officer says, "Politicians came here and accused us for harassing citizens- the issue was turned around we were seen as had no good intention to fishers, they defended the fishers instead" (*walikuja wanasiasa hapa wakavasha moto, wakatushutumu sisi kwamba tunanyanyasa wavuvi*). Fisheries officers see the politicians' actions as discouraging them and create antagonist relationships between them and the fishing communities.

In interactions with respondents, it was also revealed that some politicians were perceived as impeding fisheries management efforts by "fooling" fishers (*kunwajaza ujinga wavuvi*). That such politicians were not telling fishers the truth. An example was given that in the context of declining fish resources, instead of telling fishers the reality and that they should stop illegal fishing practices to conserve the resources, the politician was telling fishers to continue with their fishing practices, as DA makes it;-

I recall in one village meeting in 2021, the ward councillor told the fisheries officer to stop seizing illegal fishing gear, that for the time being, the

fishers have no alternative fishing gear. But for how long they will be given time? For years here, people are saying the same thing: "Let us give them time" (IDI/BMU officials)

Conversations with respondents noted that some political leaders use fisheries issues for their political interests. To not lose their influence in the villages and, for that matter, leading them to lose voters during elections, some politicians would always make influential decisions that align with voters' interests, making voters feel happy. Thus, in the context of declining fish resources, fishers wish to take whatever can be taken in the Ocean; as a result, politicians wish to please their voters for fear of losing voters' trust. In a focus group discussion, respondents had the following to say:-

"We all understand that fish resources are declining and that we need to take action to improve fisheries management; however, some political leaders, because of their personal interest of staying in power, are ready to defend illegal fishing practices, claiming that his/ her people have no other sources of income. But we are knowledgeable; we realise that politicians wanted just to please people win them- make them feel that he is a good leader who cares about their needs. These contribute to a continued decline in fish catches" (FGD/fishers/ Kipumbwi/ 2021).

Another respondent added:

"I have been fishing in this Ocean for over 20 years now; what I can say is that we have been misled by politicians for a long time. If you listen to what they say, you wonder what kind of leaders are these? We all know that some fishing gears or practices have been banned by the government, but you may hear some politicians defend such practices. Then you can realise that they are doing that for personal interests" (FGD/fishers/ Kipumbwi/ 2021).

This quote implies that, fishers understand what they are supposed to do in order to ensure sustainable fisheries resources. That they realize fishing practices would lead to decline in fish resources. That's why they are able to note the deceiving messages of politicians. Even if some fishers were influenced by the statements of

politicians, still they were knowledgeable of what is supposed to be.

On the other hand, it was noted that some political leaders own fishing gear and some of them were said to be illegal fishing gear – "*kuna viongozi wamekuwa wamiliki zana haramu kwa muda mrefu tu*"- denoting that there are leaders who have been owning illegal fishing gears for years. Such leaders are believed to influence fisheries management decisions in favour of their interests. The tendency of politician to own fishing gears (including illegal ones) was mentioned in all study sited. One fisheries officer in the research areas mentioned that most political leaders who own fishing gears work underground (*anafanya kichini chini*) to make sure that decisions that are likely to affect their interests, whether at ward or district level, are not passed and even if they are passed, their implementation become complicated (*vinawekwa vikwazo vya kutekeleza maamuzi kama hayo*). Additionally, it was revealed that some political leaders have the tendency to reveal the secrets of decision-making bodies to fishers for their interests, as Mr FJ, a BMU leader, makes it:

"Some political leaders have been revealing the secrets about our plans. Happened several times. Once, we planned in the ward meeting that we are going to seize illegal fishing gear, and when we went for that at night, we found no fisher (kila tukienda kukamata tunaambulia patupu). Later on, it became known that one of the political leaders in our area was behind this" (IDI/BMU leader/ 2021).

Equally, respondents have observed that some political leaders engage in illegally transporting fish products. These leaders were referred to as "wapenda rushwa" (lit. corruption lovers' leaders) –they were making deals with fish traders from different countries to export fish products illegally. Such leaders also collaborate with officials in the control and surveillance units. Respondents were in view that these, among other things, are discouraging community members from adopting sustainable fishing practices, as one BMU leader puts it:

"Some leaders here collaborate with people to transport illegally fish products to other regions or

even neighbouring countries. That's why when we meet in meetings to discuss how to deal with the problem, some leaders are not interested in discussing such things; they just say, "This is the role of the government" (biyo ni kazi ya serikali). But we all know that even the Fisheries Act clearly shows that BMU should work with other authorities to manage fish resources (IDI/BMU leaders/ 2021).

Fishers also perceived political leaders as not having tangible plans to improve the well-being of fishers. Fishers felt to be left behind in terms of assistance from the government. In the conversation with respondents, some compared themselves to farmers. Fishers thought that the government had forgotten them and that it took care of the farmers and had nothing to do with fishers than collecting revenue from them through licensing. In an interview, one had the following comments:

"We don't know what the government thinks about us, we have been giving money to the government through license, but the government has no help to fishers (sisi tumekuwa tunatoa fedha za leseni serikalini lakini serikalali haina msaada wowote kwetu wavuvi). We are here in destitute condition like a child who has neither father nor mother. The farmers are given fertilisers, and they are given tractors on a loan basis, but nothing is given to a fisherman; instead of being assisted, every year, we experience tax increment. We are not even involved in plans to change taxes as opposed to farmers who through their bodies participate in the planning" (IDI/fishers/Bagamoyo).

Fisheries managers at the district levels also shared similar observations with fishers about the government. In interviews with district fisheries officers, they commented that of all the sectors in the country, the fisheries sector receives little attention from the government. One noted that, "the eyes of the government are upon big sectors like mineral and tourism not on fisheries sector" (*macho ya serikali inaangalia sana sekta kubwa kubwa kama madini na utalii sio sekta ya uvuvi*). According to the fisheries officers, the problems resulting from this "behavior" of the government include under staffing fisheries

officers, weak control and surveillance and little incentives for fishers to take part in co-management initiatives.

From the discussions with respondents, it was noted that my respondents had negative perceptions about fisheries management as they feel that the government does not care what is happening to them (*serikali haina msaada wowote*). The political leaders were also blamed for making deceiving promises to fishers. They have been promising to present their problems to the upper authorities, such as the parliament, for the sake of improving the fisheries sector, but nothing has happened:

"I think fishers are the the groups which have been left alone. We have many problems here: high license charges, taxes, and illegal fishing practices. We don't have any hope. Our leaders are there to meet their interests, not to help us. When the election comes, they come here with many promises, but after the election they disappear; the situation remains the same. If I were to be asked about the need for a government, I would ask them to leave us alone to determine their destination (serikali ituache tufanye tunavyojua sisi)" (IDI/fishers/Bagamoyo).

This study was also interested in understanding respondents' perception of politics' influence on fisheries management in the study communities. Respondents were asked to provide their views about the messages and behaviours of politicians. It was revealed that a politician has a great influence on fisheries management, leading to increased non-conformity to fisheries regulations, as Mzee Moga noted;-

"To be sincere, most fishers here know the fisheries regulations, including BMU by-laws. We know that some fishers are engaging themselves in illegal fishing practices. But it is not that they don't know what they are supposed to do; they know they do so with a clear understanding of laws and the impact of their actions on the environment. The big challenge we have now is the politicians, who may provide statements that defend unsustainable practices in the name of "letting people earn their living". Some politicians discourage efforts and plans aiming to address illegal fishing. Their

messages fuel illegal fishing practices in our Ocean (IDI/fisher/Kipumbwi)."

The above quote implies that fishers understand very well what is supposed to be done concerning fisheries management. In conversations with respondents it was noted that, a lot of efforts has been done by government through BMUs to improve fisheries management in the Ocean; however, these efforts has been turned down by some politicians. It was further noted that, since politicians are influential in the society they largely affected sustainable fisheries initiatives. On the other hand, (as noted above) fishers are aware of the impact of unsustainable fisheries practices, but due to decline in fish catches and limited alternative sources of income, they choose to engage in unsustainable fisheries practices. Additionally, politicians further worsen the situations as some fishers who wish to catch whatever can be caught, feel backed-up by some politicians.

Discussion

This study aimed to understand how politics influence fisheries management. Findings from this study revealed that politician and politics have a great influence on fisheries management. As indicated in the findings, some politicians discouraged fisheries officers who were working hard to halt illegal fishing activities in the Ocean for their political interests, such as making people feel that the political leaders like them. This was used also as a way to influence people during elections. This tactic has been noted by other researchers as well. For example, Benjaminsen et al. (2009) assert that politicians used divisive tactics to win local elections.

The current study has also demonstrated that some politicians were owning illegal fishing gears and were using them for fishing activities. This implies that, such political leaders are working against sustainable fisheries management. This is because, such politicians could hardly support any effort to seize illegal fishing gears. Ownership of illegal fishing gears by some leaders and politicians has been noted by other

studies and have been linked to failures of sustainable fisheries management (see, Obiero et al. 2015, Petit and Shipton, 2012)

Findings in this study has demonstrated the fact that some politicians were discouraging the efforts of fisheries officers and BMUs. As it has been indicated in the findings, some politicians approached fisheries officers acusing them for harrasing fishers; however, in real terms, fisheries officers were implementing fisheries regulations. BMU committee members expressed their frusturations from politicians who were working against the efforts of BMU, contributing to failures of BMU. This findings relate with the study by Obiero et al. 2015; Luomba et al. 2016). who noted that BMUs in Lake Victoria failed to enforce fisheries regulations and by-laws. Our findings asserts that failures of BMUs may be due to the influence of politicians (among other factors).

Conclusion

Politics plays a significant role in influencing fisheries management. The findings of this study indicate that messages and behaviours of some political leaders contributed to non-conformity among fishers in the study areas, consequently jeopardising sustainable management initiatives. This was because, some fishers used political statements were used to justify their action of violating fisheries regulations. On the other hand, politicians discouraged fisheries officers committed to enforcing fisheries regulations. This study concludes that, as opposed to what fishers have been perceived (as reluctant to observe fisheries regulations and therefore blamed for declining fish catches and unsustainable fisheries practices), we argue that other factors, such as politics, play a significant role in daunting sustainable fisheries management efforts. To improve fisheries management, governments need to consider the influence of politics on fisheries management and strategise ways to minimise the influence of politics on fisheries management.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest

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